

HR MANAGEMENT AND COACHING IN THE INNOVATIVE ECONOMY AS A METHOD OF BUSINESS MANAGEMENT

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Abstract. *In this article, the effectiveness of the company in the conditions of the innovative economy, the problems of the application of HR management by the business entities of our country in their activities, the recommendations regarding the effectiveness of the application of HR management and coaching in the entrepreneurial activities of the innovative economy are mentioned.*

Key words: *innovative economy, coaching, HR management, three-dimensional (3D) coaching process, GROW technique, ABC technique, business environment, human resources management.*

УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ПЕРСОНАЛОМ И КОУЧИНГ В ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ КАК МЕТОД УПРАВЛЕНИЯ БИЗНЕСОМ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассмотрены эффективность деятельности компании в условиях инновационной экономики, проблемы применения HR-менеджмента субъектами предпринимательства нашей страны в их деятельности, рекомендации по эффективности применения HR-менеджмента и коучинга в упоминается предпринимательская деятельность инновационной экономики.*

Ключевые слова: *инновационная экономика, коучинг, управление персоналом, трехмерный (3D) коучинговый процесс, методика GROW, методика ABC, бизнес-среда, управление человеческими ресурсами.*

In the innovative economy, many managers are faced with the problem of a low level of creative activity of employees, which reduces the efficiency of the company. Statistics show that 94% of the world's 500 most successful companies use coaching in their work. Our country is at the beginning of the development of coaching culture. Business entities of our country face a number of problems in the process of applying HR management in their activities. First, the most used organizational management methods in companies are inconsistent.

For example, planning the organization's activities based on the existing situation and resources does not allow an entrepreneur to act in conditions of extreme uncertainty and achieve high results. Secondly, the business entities of our country are faced with administrative tyranny and corruption in the implementation of contractual relations with various higher organizations.

But foreign experience shows that the use of coaching by leading Western business entities operating in countries with an established innovation economy is considered to be of particular importance. Coaching is a purposeful process of developing the potential of employees to maximize their personal effectiveness and the success of the organization as a whole.

The most common areas of application of coaching in a modern organization cover different levels of management: from personnel management, operational management to strategic management.

The company's competitive advantage lies in the formation of proactive and active employees with extremely high work efficiency, because even small investments in them multiply according to their desires, formed by coaching, and give high financial and economic results.

On the part of business entities, there are a number of stages in establishing a relationship between Coaching and the client.

1. Making a "contract" to jointly achieve a specific goal.
2. Determination of intermediate tasks.
3. Study of the current situation.
4. Identification of internal and external obstacles to achieving the goal.
5. Analysis of potential opportunities for overcoming obstacles.
6. An agreement between the coaching and the client on what exactly needs to be done for each of their meetings.
7. Implementation of employee development plan by using specific methods.
8. Evaluation of the results of the coaching process.

It is proposed to combine these stages into a three-dimensional (3D) model of the coaching process, the stages of which determine the effectiveness of the measures taken and the investments made. In the first stage of coaching, the process of interaction between the coachee and the client takes place, during which the necessary information is collected and the current situation is analyzed, as a result of which mutual understanding is established and cooperation begins.

The second stage is dedicated to planning the system of actions to achieve the set goals. At this stage, the client must take responsibility for the outcome and plan the coaching process.

In the third stage of coaching, the client's development plan is implemented using specific coaching techniques. The most popular coaching methods are 3D technique (three-dimensional technique), GROW technique and ABC technique. Finally, in the fourth stage, the results of achieving the client's development goals are evaluated, the results of the coaching process are summarized, and the effectiveness of the investments made in this process is determined.

The main goal of using coaching by business entities is to make coaching an integral part of the work of the HR department, to offer it to managers as one of the tools of the management style, and to make it a part of the corporate culture.

The procedure for implementing coaching includes four areas of work:

Thus, in the initiation and implementation of large projects in the field of human resources development, special attention should be paid to the description of procedures and the creation of tools for the implementation of the project. There are no well-defined rules that can prevent employees from accepting initiatives that are beneficial to the organization. Introducing coaching to the organization as an independent type of management allows turning all processes of the organization into innovative conditions of the new knowledge economy. At the same time, the costs of implementing this technology significantly exceed the results, because they are based on the achievement of personal goals of employees, which creates an additional intangible motivation system for work.

Thus, in the process of studying the existing methods of managing the organization in the innovative economy, their problems and prospects for their use were identified. In today's competitive business environment, business owners must constantly improve their skills, knowledge and performance to stay ahead of the competition. Coaching can help entrepreneurs achieve this goal by providing personal guidance, feedback, and support to develop leadership, management, and problem-solving skills.

Business coaching has a significant impact on the overall success and development of business entities. When businesses invest in coaching, they provide themselves and their employees with valuable tools and resources to improve performance and productivity.

There are four main areas where business coaching can have an impact:

1. Improved efficiency and productivity.
2. Advanced decision-making skills.
3. Increased employee attraction and retention.
4. Improved communication and collaboration.

Improved Efficiency and Productivity: One of the main benefits of business coaching is its ability to help individuals and teams improve their efficiency and productivity. Through guidance and support, business coaching helps businesses identify areas of difficulty and develop strategies to improve performance. This can lead to increased productivity and improved quality of work, ultimately improving the bottom line of the business.

Enhanced Decision-Making Skills: Business coaching can also help business owners and teams develop decision-making skills. By teaching entrepreneurs how to analyze situations, identify potential risks, and make informed decisions, coaching can help businesses make more effective decisions. This can lead to better results and improved business results.

Increased employee engagement and retention: Business coaching can also have a positive impact on employee engagement and retention. Engaged employees are more productive, innovative, and report greater job satisfaction. Through coaching, a business entity can learn how to delegate tasks to employees so that they become more empowered in their roles. This can lead to increased employee retention and a stronger company culture.

Improved communication and collaboration: Finally, business coaching can help improve communication and collaboration within a company. Coaching helps reduce misunderstandings and conflicts by teaching the business entity how to communicate effectively, leading to smoother and more effective teamwork. Improved collaboration can lead to better decision-making, greater innovation and improved business results.

Business coaching can have a significant impact on the success and development of a company. By investing in coaching, business owners can improve productivity, improve decision-making skills, increase and retain employee engagement, and improve communication and collaboration within the company.

Coaching can significantly impact business success by developing leadership skills, improving goal setting and strategic planning, increasing innovation and creativity, and improving financial performance.

Based on the above analytical data, we would like to give the following recommendations in order to increase the efficiency of the use of coaching in HR management by business entities.

1. The company's greater focus on HR goals

Human resource management bridges the gap by incorporating goal setting into their performance management processes, linking individual and team goals of employees with overall organizational goals. Goals are an important part of creating a culture of transparency and accountability where employees are united in helping the company achieve long-term success.

2. Increase employee activity

It's hard to overstate the power of employee engagement—and it's been a top priority for HR professionals for the past few years. Leadership coaching increases productivity, improves communication, employee loyalty, and reduces stress and tension levels within companies.

3. More efficient selection of employees

Effective HRM strategies include many processes that have been proven to improve performance:

Setting and tracking goals can motivate employees to work harder to achieve them.

When you invest in your employees, they invest their skills, energy and time in your company.

4. Increase customer loyalty

If your customers are invested in achieving their goals, feel a sense of belonging in the workplace, and identify with your company's values, they will generally be satisfied, productive employees—and customers will notice.

Coaching helps managers improve interpersonal relationships. Some common causes of interpersonal conflict include leaders who are too unreasonable, too controlling, and too isolated. So coaches work with people to explore these behaviors and to recognize and change their self-defeating beliefs, assumptions, and actions.

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